

Western Sydney's Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating
Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2022 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws on prior research and engagement projects to visualise entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which teams of students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals to advance the ecosystem.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

General Methodology

In partnership with Investment NSW (e.g., Sydney Startup Hub) and Spark Festival, the cohort of ~45 students was given the option to focus on Sydney CBD, Western Sydney, or Nationally. Additionally, one team was based overseas and was free to choose an international city to navigate.

The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,³ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE).

In addition to learning about ecosystems, teams engaged with ecosystems in authentic and immersive learning experiences. Stakeholder types and specific stakeholders in the ecosystem were identified based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. Insights about the ecosystem were generated by analysing desktop reports and media interviews involved those stakeholders. Where possible, teams conducted their own interviews of key stakeholders, including asking them about the ecosystem's history, evolution and critical events, and their vision for how it may evolve further. By synthesising such reports and interviews from multiple stakeholders, teams developed a composite story of the ecosystem's evolution, visualised its current state and identified specific opportunities for change. These reports present this analysis of the ecosystems' evolution as well as the team's proposal for specific interventions by which to intentionally advance the ecosystem in a specific direction.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Ecosystem Definition

The Western Sydney Entrepreneurial Ecosystem encompasses the vast geographic region of Western Sydney which is 9,000 square kilometres spanning over 13 local government councils (Profile ID, n.d) [Figure 1]. Statistically, it is more disadvantaged and diverse compared to Metropolitan Sydney in terms of employment rates, educational levels, and household income (King et al., 2016).

Western Sydney Startup Hub (WSSH) is an expansion of the Sydney Startup Hub (SSH) which will be a key piece of infrastructure for connecting and growing entrepreneurs in Western Sydney. WSSH runs in line with the NSW government's plan to develop and service the growing population of Western Sydney to bring more opportunities closer to home (Deloitte, 2016). The challenge will be ensuring whether the Western Sydney community will utilise and benefit from this investment.

We identified the health and technology industries (med-tech) as key fields in the ecosystem because of the prominence of workers within these sectors in Western Sydney (King et al., 2019; Hyland, 2022). The manufacturing sector has been the main job industry for Western Sydney workers, however within the last 20 years there has been a substantial increase in locally based health and tech jobs (Business Western Sydney, 2022). This trend will hope to service the Westmead Health and Innovation District (WHID) composed of major hospitals and medical research institutes (Deloitte, 2016) to generate innovative healthcare solutions and accelerate economic growth (NSW Government, n.d.).

2 Ecosystem Timeline

2013

The Westmead Alliance was formed, a group of 18 organisations including major hospitals, health organisations, research institutes, government bodies, and educational institutes. These organisations include the Western Sydney Local Health District, Sydney Children's Hospitals Network, Westmead Institute for Medical Research, Westmead Private Hospital, the University of Sydney, Cumberland Council, City of Parramatta Council and Sydney Business Chamber. The creation of this alliance serves a great importance to the ecosystem as these stakeholders hold interests in contributing to the growth of health innovation in Western Sydney, providing a unified voice and long-term perspective to innovation-related investments and decisions (Westmead Alliance, n.d.).

2015

Western Sydney University (WSU) is the dominant tertiary institution in Western Sydney with campuses throughout the region including Bankstown, Parramatta, and Campbelltown. WSU's start-up incubator 'Launch Pad', formed in 2015, has established a strong student-run entrepreneurial ecosystem within Western Sydney. Launch Pad has enabled entrepreneurs to grow their businesses by providing a vast range of support through mentorships, programs, events, networking, training, and education as well as co-working offices, collaborative spaces and cutting-edge facilities located in the Parramatta CBD (WSU, n.d.). This was a progressive initiative that invested in student potential towards innovation and entrepreneurship which WSSH should consider incorporating. While this has progressively produced several start-ups in the region, it is confined to the university environment and isolated from the rest of the ecosystem (WSU, n.d.).

2020

Launch Pad was awarded a \$250,000 grant to develop the 'SydWest Global Connections Tech Start-up' program, an accelerator initiative to support entrepreneurs within the Western Sydney precinct and drive the development of technology-based start-up companies. This project was recognised through the Australian Government Entrepreneurs' Programme to connect entrepreneurs and founders with training, mentoring and business development opportunities (Sardya, 2020). This grant specifically targeted and contributed to the expansion of tech-based start-ups within Western Sydney's entrepreneurial ecosystem.

2022

Architecture and planning company Urbis is assisting with the planning of the WSSH (Urbis, n.d.) [Figure 2, 3 and 4]. It is currently undergoing restorative work and is set to open later this year (A. Quah, personal communication, July 8, 2022). Urbis' involvement in the project will likely end after the renovations are complete, unless things need to be changed or updated in the future.

2022

WSU has partnered with Charter Hall to construct Westmead Innovation Quarter which is a medical and education research centre located in the heart of Westmead, dedicated to deliver health, social and economic benefits to the Western Sydney community. \$350 million has been invested into the centre with goals to aid Australia's brightest minds from healthcare, industry, and government in discovering new heights of health and medical breakthroughs to create solutions to some of our most pressing health challenges. The Westmead Innovation Quarter will provide leading edge technologies to foster STEM-related innovation and commercialisation to ultimately create a new research environment for the benefit of the Western Sydney's entrepreneurial ecosystem (WSU, n.d.).

2.1 Present Stage

The entrepreneurial ecosystem within Western Sydney is still in its early stages of growth (D. Jozic & D. Ngo, personal communication, July 8, 2022). Meanwhile, the NSW Government is currently in the process of selecting an operator to work alongside it on the WSSH (NSW Government, n.d.). The NSW government will provide the space, facilities, staffing, grants, programs, and connections to the existing NSW Start-up community such as the SSH (NSW Government, n.d.). As a culturally significant and valuable heritage site to the local community, a major part of the evaluation criteria will assess the

community contributions of the operators and their plans to attract Western Sydney start-ups to reside at the Hub (NSW Government, n.d).

Based on our first-hand interviews with identified key stakeholders, the Greater Cities Commission, WHID and Western Sydney entrepreneurs, we were able to receive insights into barriers to entrepreneurship. While the government has ambitious plans for the Western Sydney region, our interviewees highlighted some key challenges:

1. There is a stigma especially within the migrant community that start-ups are high-risk largely because of their lack of access to funding and resources (D. Jozic & D. Ngo, personal communication, July 8, 2022).
2. Due to the high capital cost of operating a start-up, many people within the Western Sydney community rely on full-time jobs for funding. Therefore, they have limited time to dedicate to pursuing business ideas (A. Quah, personal communication, July 8, 2022).
3. Lack of qualified and competent workforce, particularly workers with scientific and business skills and experience (D. Cartoso, personal communication, July 6, 2022)
4. Lack of investor funding (D. Cartoso, personal communication, July 6, 2022)

It is in the hubs best interest to avoid or at least approach these challenges with a positive intention. However, we must trust that choosing to incorporate a hub in Western Sydney was not a decision made without justification. As proved by our research we have determined that Western Sydney is a more than sufficient location for a start-up hub and should show success over the next few years.

Figure 1: Western Sydney Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map

3 Ecosystem Map

The map in Figure 1 highlights our understanding of the current entrepreneurial ecosystem in Western Sydney, in relation to the med-tech industry. It includes the various stakeholders who are active in the ecosystem, which stakeholder elements are involved and the connections between these organisations.

3.1 Stakeholders

The map is made up of various stakeholders involved in the ecosystem. These stakeholders have been identified as playing some role or having an impact, small and large, on the ecosystem. These organisations were identified in our research about the ecosystem, particularly when investigating the history of the ecosystem, what resources are available in the area, and in interviews with Carol Friel, Maxine Sherrin, Andrew Quah, Davor Jozic and Daniel Ngo.

All stakeholders in our map are involved in the entrepreneurial ecosystem we defined above. Most are physically located in, and all work or provide resources to the Western Sydney geographical area. Several stakeholders included are also part of the med-tech industry. 'Med-Tech' is a colloquial term for the medical and technology industry and comprises everything medical or technological. Choosing to focus on this industry, as it is a prevalent sector in Western Sydney, narrowed the very large geographical boundaries of Western Sydney to certain stakeholders. It provided a focus to our research and which stakeholders were included in the map. However, the med-tech industry is broad enough that there are enough stakeholders in the area and include both medical entrepreneurship and technological entrepreneurship, which is a large part of Western Sydney investment and innovation.

In our map, the stakeholders we believe are the most important, due to their wide range of connections to other organisations and resources or knowledge they provide to the ecosystem are bold and in a larger box. By visually emphasising the key stakeholders, the user is drawn to these organisations first, giving them a place to start working through the map.

3.2 Stakeholder Features

We divided our stakeholders from our research into seven main stakeholder elements. These elements are evident using assorted colours in the visual. These elements represent various parts of the ecosystem, all of which are necessary for an active and interconnected ecosystem (Woolley, 2017). By highlighting the different elements stakeholders fall into, one can easily identify the functions of the stakeholders and how many stakeholders there are in each element, presenting the question of whether those elements are ones that need to be focused on. The stakeholder elements we choose to include in our map are based on Stam and Ven's entrepreneurial ecosystem model (2021) and highlight the different activities stakeholders are engaging in in the ecosystem. These elements are:

- **Leadership:** which includes stakeholders who provide guidance for and promote entrepreneurialism and start-ups.
- **Finance:** who are organisations that provide funding or investment into the ecosystem.
- **Education:** which are the formal educational institutes that promote or educate Western Sydney students about entrepreneurialism and its importance.
- **Infrastructure:** which includes stakeholders that provide, manage or fund physical spaces or resources that allow for people to collaborate and innovate.
- **Community:** which is the general population and businesses in Western Sydney. These people impact the culture of the area and are potential customers for entrepreneurial ideas and products.
- **Entrepreneurs:** who are start-ups, incubators, accelerators, or stakeholders that practice entrepreneurialism.
- **Health:** who are organisations in the health industry, for example hospitals and medical research facilities.

3.3 Interconnections

It is important to show the different interconnections between stakeholders on a stakeholder map because it can add a layer of depth to the information. The stakeholders' interconnections can vary depending on a variety of factors like permeance, history or value. For this stakeholder map and its legibility, the connections between stakeholders are divided up into three categories. The thick line is any connection directly between two significant stakeholders. The thin line are strong connections between other stakeholders, while the dashed line is a weak connection between the other stakeholders.

To define a strong connection, we explored permanent connections and who has the most to gain from the Western Sydney Entrepreneurial Ecosystem Map. While a weak connection is defined by connections that are 'one-off' or intermittent. Considering the ecosystem is still new and is not that far developed yet we are not defining connections as 'strong' based on how long they have been connected. This may, however, be a definition that can be incorporated later, in the ecosystem's span once a few of the stakeholders have been involved for a significant period. Over the next ten years, we will see what these stakeholders achieve and ideally, they will create a connected community around entrepreneurialism, producing some success stories that can be used in the future to encourage new innovators.

4 Our Vision

Our vision for the Western Sydney Entrepreneurial Ecosystem is to become an integrated and inclusive system that fully services, connects, inspires and future-proofs not only Western Sydney entrepreneurs but the greater Western Sydney Community. Our vision will transcend diversity to be inclusive to all including those that are unemployed, the immigrant population, Aboriginal and Indigenous people, primary, secondary, and tertiary students, as well as those seeking a career change. We hope the ecosystem becomes active and connected as there is currently a disconnect between the different networks of start-ups within Western Sydney (Maxine Sherrin, personal communication, 28 June 2022).

4.1 Challenges

For this vision to come true, the current educational system, and skills and capacities of workers in Western Sydney will need to be improved. To promote innovation and foster experience and entrepreneurial skills, there will need to be a collaborative effort between educational systems, industry partners and the community. This opportunity to facilitate the gap in awareness about innovation and entrepreneurial skills in the region will hopefully produce jobs, particularly as the Western Sydney population is growing at an exponential rate, predicted to reach 8 million within 40 years (Greater Cities Commission, n.da). The education system needs to be equipped to meet the labour demands of the future. Education will be critical to the development of the Western Sydney entrepreneurial ecosystem not only because of improving skill development, but also in creating awareness and interest in entrepreneurial opportunities.

5 Lever 1: Skill Development

Proposal 1 is to introduce and develop STEM (Science Technology Engineering Maths) and entrepreneurial skills to encourage careers in key start-up industries such as health and technology. ENTRYpreneur is a program of face-to-face activities aimed to accelerate ideas no matter who you are in society. This aims to lower the barriers to entry for entrepreneurship. Activities and programs will be based on an individual's current knowledge, experience and skill level divided into three zones. We are particularly targeting primary, secondary, and tertiary students, people not studying that want to upskill, those wanting a career change, immigrants, and the Aboriginal and Indigenous population. The Red Zone will introduce foundational STEM and entrepreneurial skills to those completely new to entrepreneurship. The Yellow Zone is for individuals with a greater interest in innovation and entrepreneurialism who wish to develop their skills, knowledge, and experience further. The Green Zone is for those assessed to be work-force ready or who want to run their own start-up.

Figure 2: Three zones of entrepreneurial skills development

5.1 The Greater Sydney Innovation Co-Operative (Co-Operative)

We propose for these programs to be run by the Co-Operative. The Co-Operative is a group of members dedicated to the promotion of the tech and innovation ecosystem in Western Sydney, formed as an initiative to operate the WSSH (Greater Sydney Innovation Co-Operative, 2022). We believe the Co-Operative is a good pick to run these programs as they can use their existing networks and resources like accelerators and start-ups (e.g. Catalysr), the SSH, investors, and government to establish these activities and workshops (A. Quah, personal communication, July 8, 2022). The Co-Operative can also utilise their connections to WHID to support excursions for school children to provide insight into practical applications of innovation and research.

The Co-Operative's vision is to ensure that jobs are brought closer and developed to where people live. Our proposal of stimulating the mindsets of the general population in Western Sydney and generating talk

around entrepreneurship and the STEM sector through these activities and workshops, will future proof the jobs for Western Sydney. As the community becomes more informed, there will be more interest around innovation and STEM. The more interest garnered around these sectors will pique interest in entering these fields and creating their own careers. Rather than having the community travel to the Sydney CBD for services and facilities, they can access the same services in Western Sydney with significantly less travel time and costs (Business Western Sydney, 2022), hence fulfilling the Co-Operative's purpose of flexibility for the community.

5.2 NSW Government & Local Governments

We propose for the NSW Government and the LGA (Local Government Areas) councils to fund the operation of ENTRYpreneur. Access to these programs should be of minimal cost which is where the government and councils can subsidise ENTRYpreneur. This is because "the highest rates of households from... diverse backgrounds who live in low- income households are clustered in... Western Sydney" (NCOSS, 2019). Providing more accessible services and programs to the general population will ensure everyone will benefit from these opportunities. These programs can help facilitate job creation for the predicted population growth of 1 million people in the next 15 years (Deloitte, 2016) and can help solve issues within the community, thus be of benefit to local governments. These workshops will contribute to Investment NSW's vision to support economic growth, as it will allow people to grow connections and interact with each other. These interactions may facilitate the development of innovative ideas and products, resulting in increasing productivity and economic growth (ECB, 2019).

6 Lever 2: Integrated Online Presence

To create an awareness of entrepreneurial and STEM-related skills, we propose to build a strong online community that compliments the physical space and resources in the area and bring the community closer together. This will include a website and TV channel like Spark TV, a YouTube channel developed by Spark Festival because of the COVID-19 pandemic (M. Sherrin, personal communication, June 28, 2022).

The TV channel will appeal to the diverse community and will be running a range of programs 24/7 including stories about multicultural entrepreneurs, online workshops to develop entrepreneurial skills, advertisements for ENTRYpreneur and information about the Western Sydney ecosystem. There will also be subtitles and dubbing in the most prevalent languages in Western Sydney such as Mandarin, Cantonese, Arabic, Hindi and Korean (ABS, 2016). In conjunction with the TV channel, it will be streamed online (on Freeview TV and its own website) and distributed to radio stations, with some content also developed into podcasts.

The initial stages of the rollout of the TV channel will be in three stages:

- Stage 1:
 - Translation and interpretation of content on Spark TV.
- Stage 2:
 - Introduction of content on Spark TV on existing council TV channels such as the Canterbury-Bankstown TV (CBTV).
 - Creation of a website where content can be streamed, and podcasts found.
- Stage 3:
 - Staggered introduction of the TV channel to other LGA councils.
 - Introduction of other programs and content

6.1 Spark Festival

Spark Festival is a key stakeholder we have interest in to participate in our proposal. We would like to caption and dub the content on Spark TV using funding provided by the local governments. When we reach Stage 2, we need the permission of Spark Festival to introduce this content on CBTV. This proposal would be beneficial to the Spark Festival as it allows them to become in contact with diverse actors who may express interest in the Spark Festival. This corresponds with Spark Festival's vision of "driv[ing] prosperity for all Australians via the growth of thriving new economy businesses" (Spark Festival, n.d.). These translation and interpretation mechanisms can also be utilised for events run by Spark Festival ensuring the festival becomes more inclusive of the community.

6.2 Greater Sydney Innovation Co-Operative

It would be in our interest to have the Co-Operative running the TV channel. Their "formidable coalition [with] industry and community partners" (Greater Sydney Innovation Co-Operative, n.d.) will be extremely useful in attracting start-ups and incubators to create content and promote their services or products. Andrew Quah has worked with entrepreneurs and the local community for many years including Maxine Sherrin and Omar Najjar (A. Quah, personal communication, July 8, 2022). He has the network, knowledge and experience being an entrepreneur himself to promote and produce content that is appropriately targeted towards Western Sydney and its needs. Our proposal aims to remove the barriers associated with entrepreneurship particularly in Western Sydney, as it is easily available to everyone and will promote entrepreneurial ideas. Thus, by promoting innovation, it will ensure more collaboration between people and organisations, which correlates with the Co-Operative's concerns of Western Sydney falling behind in the innovation world due to these issues (Greater Sydney Innovation Co-Operative, n.d.).

6.3 Local Government Councils

We propose the various LGA councils to fund and support the operation of the TV channel and, for translators and interpreters to provide subtitles and dubbing. We hope all councils can utilise their resources and connections to find translators and interpreters in the local area to initiate stage 1. Videos with subtitles or dubbing in one's respective language can increase engagement from watching without subtitles at approximately 66% to 91% with subtitles (Rev, 2019). This engagement will be key in our proposal as it will draw and attract a wider range of individuals into entrepreneurship from diverse backgrounds, thus, drawing more people into Western Sydney. This will drive more opportunities for people within Western Sydney, aligning with the Government's vision for the area. The LGA councils' roles also include servicing and being inclusive of the community (NSW Government, n.d.). This aligns with the aim of our proposal to create awareness about entrepreneurs and STEM skills to the population of Western Sydney. Removing the language barrier makes it more accessible to the community, making it more inclusive for everyone. This proposal will allow community issues to be resolved with the rise of diverse entrepreneurs, aligning with the purpose of the LGA councils.

7 Legislative Proposals: Metrics & Outcomes

The success of both proposals will be measured ongoingly and primarily through marketing metrics. Marketing materials and channels such as views on broadcasts, social media followings and interactions, and sign-ups to ENTRYpreneur programs will measure the level of outreach to the community. Direct impact will take longer and be harder to identify but will be measured by the number of applications for residency at WSSH, the attendance numbers at events and workshops, number of capital investments and interested investors. These proposals aim to reduce the number of unemployed while boosting the skills and providing resources for the underprivileged population. The expansion of networks as a result of our proposals will allow our ecosystem to flourish and strengthen.

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8 Appendices

Local Government Areas Within the Greater Western Sydney Region (Profile ID, n.d.)

1. Blacktown City
2. Blue Mountains City
3. Camden Council
4. Campbelltown City
5. City of Canterbury Bankstown
6. Cumberland Council
7. Fairfield City
8. Hawkesbury City
9. Liverpool City
10. City of Parramatta
11. Penrith City
12. The Hills Shire
13. Wollondilly Shire

Figure 2 and 3: WSSH Building (Cindy Prado, 2022)

Figure 4: WSSH Historic materials

The WSSH building is made of sandstone carved by female prisoners who left patterns to mark the sand stones they made. (Cindy Prado, 2022)

Figure 5: Monument erected to commemorate the children who were abused.

Engraved it reads "In This Place We Remember The Children Who Were Abused, Parramatta Girls Home 1887 – 1974, Kambala & Taldree 1975 – 1983" (Cindy Prado, 2022)

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